

Development and Implementation of an AI Enabled Virtual and 360 Holistic Future Assessment Solution for Anxious High-Stakes Examination-Deprived Post-16 Students in the Wake of the Pandemic: The Future - Exam Virtual Mind Palace.

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Submission type

Individual

Abstract

The impact of the pandemic on students and providers in further education (FE) and skills is well-documented. The education sector's digital response emerged as a significant differentiating factor during the crisis, with a focus on skill level, methodology, and curriculum design to reduce the impact on students' learning. Institutions sought to implement scalable solutions to fill the void, with Microsoft Teams and Google Classroom becoming the main institutional responses. As stated in Microsoft's 2022 position paper on 'Education Reimagined', 'The fallout from Covid-19, continuing advances in digital technology, and intensifying pent-up demand for student-centered learning have combined to present an opportunity to transform education across whole systems.' Many third-party digital applications (Quizlet, Kahoot) also saw a significant upturn in usage. However, due to cross-contamination concerns as well as expense, virtual reality activities, even though seeing a rise in wider society, took a significant hit in educational settings. These choices often depended on the individual institutions or the practitioners within, based on their own repertoire and skill level. The EdTech Demonstrator Programme made progress in providing peer-to-peer support with evidence of impact in five key areas: enhancing student results, lightening the load for teachers, aiding in the execution of school and college improvement strategies, resource management, and ensuring curriculum accessibility and inclusivity (DoE, 2022).

The negative impact on students has cast a long shadow from a social, psychological, and interpersonal skills perspective. These findings were also reported by the international educational community (Mosleh, 2022). Anxiety was the most prevalent issue. The heightened sense of isolation brought on by the pandemic, coupled with the less effective nature of online teaching, the rising risk of unemployment, and the uncertainty about what lies ahead, collectively intensified the anxiety and stress levels among students (Klasser, 2022). Students sitting examinations (A-Levels, G.C.S.E) were affected by the strain of either not being able to sit their examinations at all or examination boundary changes and adaptations to assessment to try to compensate for their disrupted education. Already disadvantaged and SEND students were still the hardest hit (Ofqual, 2021). This cohort faced the additional stressor of test anxiety, with the view that students with the most went into their final exams with less knowledge (BPS, 2022).

Transitioning from the broader impacts of the pandemic on education, this research aimed to delve into the specific influence of a context-specific 360-degree/virtual environment on instruction, learning, and evaluation. Utilising VR, PC and mobile-friendly The study drew upon the Method of Loci (MoL), a mnemonic device that associates items to be remembered with physical locations, and the context-dependent memory effect (Godden and Baddeley, 1975), which posits that memory recall can be enhanced by reinstating the context present during learning.

The resource developed consisted of 360/VR photos that were stitched together to reflect a student's existing schema of their classroom. The classroom is adorned with resources that are linked to their prior learning within that environment. Rooms were added for the students to navigate that provided opportunities for learning new content within the context of an environment that they would be assessed in the future, using low stakes assessment, guidance videos, artificial intelligence integration for personalised revision. The primary focus was to provide students with a way to reduce test anxiety with familiarisation to an unknown environment where they would be sitting their examinations, whilst providing them opportunities for retrieval practice and context familiarisation. The research involved a group of 10 A-Level students who used a VR/360 image to familiarise themselves with the examination room before the test. Data was collected through a self-report questionnaire. The findings strongly indicated that the VR/360 image boosted the students' confidence in

navigating the exam room, reduced their exam anxiety, and improved their overall readiness for the exam. The research also underscored some challenges and limitations of using the VR/360 image, such as technical issues, accessibility, and accuracy. The study explored the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to personalise student learning within the environment, providing a more effective learning experience. The research affirmed that VR/360 images can be a valuable tool for exam preparation and provided suggestions for enhancing their design and implementation. This study contributes to our understanding of the impact of VR/360 environments on learning, and assessment, and the potential of integrating mnemonic devices and AI in educational settings. The technology has now been applied to four other campuses with a modified focus, providing anxiety reduction for known barriers such as those on the autistic spectrum (ASD), as the value of the Mind Palace diversifies.

References

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Themes

Digital Technology and Artificial Intelligence

Second Theme

Practitioner Research

SESSION DETAILS

[P2.17 Innovating Educational Assessments in Digital and AI Era](#)

15:30-17:00

Monday, 9 September, 2024